

STUDY OF THE LASER RADIATION EFFECT IN COMBINATION WITH DOXORUBICIN ON THE SURVIVAL OF MCF7 AND MCF7DOX CULTURE CELLS

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Abstract

The use of lasers in oncology is constantly evolving. In recent years, the mechanisms of the effect of laser radiation, particularly of the infrared spectrum, on tumour cells in combination with various chemotherapeutic agents have been studied.

The aim. To study the effect of laser radiation with a wavelength of 660 and 810 nm on the survival of tumour cell cultures MCF7 and MCF7DOX in the presence of doxorubicin.

Materials and methods. Tumour cells of MCF7 and MCF7DOX cultures were cultured in DMEM medium (Biowest, France) with 10 % fetal calf serum (FST) (Biowest, France) and 40 µg/ml gentamicin (Sigma, USA). Doxorubicin was added to the cells to a final concentration of 1 µg/ml. Cells were irradiated with a laser (Photonica-Plus, Ukraine) with a wavelength of 660 and 810 nm (irradiation time – 5 min, power density – 50 mV/cm², irradiation dose 15 J/cm²). The results were recorded using a multiwell spectrophotometer (Labsystems Multiskan PLUS, Finland). Photomicrographs of cells were taken using a Carl Zeiss microscope, Germany.

Results. Cell survival assessment and morphological characteristics in micropreparations indicate the antitumor efficacy of the combined effects of laser irradiation and doxorubicin. The most pronounced cytotoxic effect on MCF7-DOX culture cells was caused by doxorubicin exposure for 90 min in combination with infrared laser irradiation ($\lambda = 810$ nm).

Conclusions. Infrared laser light synergises with the toxic effects of doxorubicin and creates favourable conditions for apoptosis of tumour cells, as evidenced by cytomorphological data.

Keywords: breast cancer, MCF-7, doxorubicin, laser irradiation, mitochondria, ROS-induced ROS release, p53, caspase-3, apoptosis.

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1. Introduction

Breast cancer (BC) is the most urgent medical and social problem. This is due to the high rates of cancer incidence among women not only in Ukraine but also in many economically developed countries. Currently, modern ideas about the molecular and genetic nature of malignant growth and the importance of hereditary factors in the predisposition to the development of BC

have been developed, and clinical and experimental research is being continued to increase the effectiveness of the treatment of this disease [1].

One of the main tasks of developing new healthcare approaches in oncology is reducing toxicity for healthy tissues while maintaining the effectiveness of treating malignant neoplasms. The progress of laser medicine has led to the emergence of fundamentally new technologies that are now successfully used in treating cancer patients [2, 3].

Nowadays, new treatment methods based on the achievements of photochemistry, photobiology and quantum physics are becoming increasingly common in clinical practice [4, 5]. Many preclinical and clinical studies have confirmed the effectiveness of treatment strategies using laser technologies, including photodynamic therapy (PDT) and photobiomodulation (PBM) [6, 7]. It can be argued that the study of the mechanisms of the effect of laser radiation on tumour cells should be continued, first of all, because there are many options for such an effect, taking into account the physical parameters of the laser [8, 9]. Secondly, the biological diversity of cancer provides researchers with almost unlimited potential for implementing various scientific strategies, including the combined effect of light energy and chemotherapeutic agents on tumour cells [10, 11].

Therefore, the study of the effect of lasers on biological objects, in particular as part of the improvement of therapeutic approaches to the treatment of current diseases, continues to be the focus of attention of researchers worldwide [12, 13]. Researchers are studying the biological effects of laser radiation with different wavelengths and using different biological objects of study [14, 15]. The ability of light energy at different parameters of irradiation to either promote cell regeneration or initiate in them the occurrence of pathological changes due to the modulation of metabolic processes is of great interest [16, 17].

The aim. To study the effect of laser radiation with a wavelength of 660 and 810 nm on the survival of tumour cells of MCF7 and MCF7DOX cultures in the presence of doxorubicin.

2. Materials and methods

MCF-7 human breast cancer cells were obtained from the Bank of cell lines from human and animal tissues of the R.E. Kavetsky Institute of Experimental Pathology, Oncology and Radiobiology National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine. Dr. Lukyanova N. Yu provided doxorubicin-resistant MCF-7/Dox subline cells. Cells were cultured in DMEM nutrient medium (Biowest, France) with 10 % fetal calf serum (FCT) (Biowest, France) and 40 µg/ml gentamicin (Sigma, USA). The studied cells were cultivated in a humidified atmosphere with 5 % CO₂ at 37 °C. Changing the medium and reseeding cells was done according to the standard method. Cells in the exponential phase of growth were used for further research.

Cells of the MCF-7 and MCF-7/Dox lines were planted in the wells of a 96-well plate in 100 µl of complete nutrient medium DMEM with the addition of 10 % FST at a concentration of 1×10^4 cells/well. The cells were incubated in a humidified atmosphere in the presence of 5 % CO₂ at 37 °C for 24 hours. The next day, 100 µl of doxorubicin solution (Ebewe, Austria) was added to the corresponding wells of the tablet to a final concentration of 1 µg/ml. Immediately after the introduction of doxorubicin, the cells were placed in a CO₂ incubator and cultured at 5 % CO₂ and 37 °C for 15, 30, 60 and 90 minutes.

After cultivation, the cells were irradiated with lasers (manufactured by «Photonica-Plus», Ukraine) with wavelengths of 660 and 810 nm: irradiation time – 5 min, power density – 50 mV/cm², irradiation dose 15 J/cm², respectively, after 15, 30, 60 and 90 minutes after the addition of doxorubicin. Also, for control, cells were separated to which DOX was not added and which were not irradiated; cells to which DOX was added and which were not irradiated; cells to which no DOX was added and which were irradiated with a laser. After the cells were irradiated, the tablets were placed in a CO₂ incubator and cultured at 5 % CO₂ and 37 °C for another 48 hours.

The survival of MCF-7 and MCF-7/Dox cells was assessed by a standard colourimetric method by staining cells with crystal violet (total number of cells by protein and DNA).

After the incubation, the nutrient medium was removed from all wells of the tablet, and 50 µl of crystal violet solution (Sigma, USA) (5 mg of dye in 1 ml of 70 % methyl alcohol) was added to the empty wells. The tablet was incubated at room temperature for 10 minutes, the dye

was removed, and the remaining dye was washed off with cold running water. The tablet was air-dried at room temperature in a dark place for 24 hours. Next, the dye was eluted with 96° ethyl alcohol (Ukrspirt, Ukraine). The results were recorded using a multiwell spectrophotometer (Lab-systems Multiskan PLUS, Finland) at an absorption wavelength of 540 nm. Photomicrographs of cells were taken using a Carl Zeiss microscope, Germany. Statistical data processing was carried out using the STATA12 program. To evaluate the comparison of statistical differences between groups, we used the Mann-Whitney test.

3. Results

The results of the experiment showed that in a culture that is sensitive to doxorubicin (MCF-7), tumour cell growth was inhibited when doxorubicin was added. At the same time, irradiation alone (without doxorubicin) did not significantly affect them (**Table 1**). After irradiating cell cultures with lasers with a wavelength of 660 nm and a wavelength of 810 nm, we observed inhibition of tumour cell growth in all modes. We recorded the most significant cytotoxic effect under the action of an infrared laser (810 nm) after 90 minutes of cultivation with doxorubicin (**Fig. 1**).

Table 1

Evaluation of the survival of MCF-7 tumour cells after irradiation with lasers of 660 and 810 nm in comparison with the control

MCF 7 (660)	M (SD)	MCF 7 (810)	M (SD)	P (M-W)
KK	1.364 (0.048)	KK	–	–
DOX	0.952 (0.02)	DOX	–	–
660	1.389 (0.04)	810	1.344 (0.041)	0.069
660 DOX 15	1.026 (0.068)	810 DOX 15	0.962 (0.007)	0.082
660 DOX 30	0.975 (0.041)	810 DOX 30	0.926 (0.038)	0.117
660 DOX 60	0.989 (0.046)	810 DOX 60	0.823 (0.041)	0.008*
660 DOX 90	0.952 (0.044)	810 DOX 90	0.812 (0.041)	0.009*

Note: * – the difference is statistically significant between groups 660/810 ($p < 0.05$, Mann-Whitney U-test)

Fig. 1. Comparison of the survival of MCF-7 tumour cells in the study groups compared to the control (KK)

The obtained data correlate with the morphological assessment of tumour cells after irradiation using light microscopy. If in the control group, MCF-7 cells showed active growth, the cells were located in a continuous layer, with the formation of anastomoses, layers, and cells of structures like symplasts, then in the group with the addition of doxorubicin, the cells were located in the form of a monolayer with a much lower density (**Fig. 2, 3**). A laser with a wavelength of 660 nm inhibited cell growth in combination with doxorubicin after all variants of chemotherapy exposure. However, the cytotoxic effect of the infrared laser (810 nm) after exposure to

doxorubicin for 60 and 90 minutes turned out to be the most pronounced. Microscopically, we observed the growth of tumour cells in the form of a mesh structure with thinning, individual anastomoses with the participation of cell processes, as well as ruptures of a complete layer of tumour cells with the formation of niches, cell stratification and the presence of individual cells in cavities (Fig. 4, 5).

Fig. 2. Photomicrograph of MCF7 cells without irradiation and doxorubicin. In active cell growth, cells are arranged in a continuous layer, with the formation of anastomoses, layering, and cells of structures like symplasts

Fig. 3. Photomicrograph of MCF7 cells without irradiation and with the addition of doxorubicin. Monolayer growth of tumour cells

Fig. 4. Photomicrograph of MCF7 cells irradiated with an infrared laser (810 nm) after 60 min with the presence of doxorubicin. The growth of tumour cells in the form of a mesh structure with thinning, individual anastomoses with the participation of cell processes

Fig. 5. Photomicrograph of MCF7 cells irradiated with an infrared laser (810 nm) after 90 min with the presence of doxorubicin. Rupture of a single layer of growing tumour cells with the formation of niches, delamination of cells and the presence of individual cells in cavities

The results were fundamentally different in a culture resistant to doxorubicin (MCF-7 DOX). Compared to the control, the $\lambda 660$ nm laser, in combination with a chemotherapeutic factor, did not cause a significant cytotoxic effect in all observation groups (**Table 2**). Instead, the $\lambda 810$ nm laser showed a marked cytotoxic effect in combination with doxorubicin after 60 and 90 minutes of cultivation with doxorubicin (**Fig. 6**).

Table 2

Evaluation of the survival of MCF-7 DOX tumour cells after irradiation with lasers of 660 and 810 nm in comparison with the control

MCF 7 DOX (660)	M (SD)	MCF 7 DOX (810)	M (SD)	P (M-W)
KK	1.226 (0.091)	KK	–	–
DOX	1.305 (0.044)	DOX	–	–
660	1.275 (0.043)	810	1.270 (0.046)	0.754
660 DOX 15	1.241 (0.072)	810 DOX 15	1.246 (0.057)	0.917
660 DOX 30	1.254 (0.036)	810 DOX 30	1.223 (0.023)	0.142
660 DOX 60	1.245 (0.064)	810 DOX 60	1.092 (0.064)	0.012*
660 DOX 90	1.234 (0.086)	810 DOX 90	1.038 (0.08)	0.016*

Note: * – the difference is statistically significant between groups 660/810 ($p < 0.05$, Mann-Whitney U-test)

Fig. 6. Comparison of MCF-7 DOX tumour cell survival in study groups versus control (KK)

According to light microscopy, MCF-7 DOX cells in the control groups, both with and without doxorubicin, showed active growth – fields of solid growth alternating with areas of rarefac-

tion (**Fig. 7, 8**). Furthermore, the most effective in terms of cytotoxic effect on the resistant culture, the infrared laser in combination with doxorubicin caused the rupture of solidly growing tumour cells with the formation of cavities and the separation of isolated groups of cells and single cells after 60 min of cultivation with the medicine (**Fig. 9**).

Fig. 7. Photomicrograph of MCF7-DOX cells without irradiation and doxorubicin.
Fields of solid growth of tumour cells

Fig. 8. Photomicrograph of MCF7-DOX cells without irradiation
and with the addition of doxorubicin. Areas of rarefaction alternating with solid areas
of growth of tumour cells

Fig. 9. Photomicrograph of MCF7-DOX cells irradiated with an infrared laser (810 nm)
with 90 min of doxorubicin. Loss of connections between growing tumour cells
with the formation of large cavity structures in which cell groups and individual cells
are defined, cells with torn membranes and stratified cytoplasm (necrosis, apoptosis),
and the appearance of giant tumour cells with large nuclei are observed

The loss of connections between tumour cells with the formation of large cavity structures, in which groups of cells and individual cells were determined after 90 min of cultivation with the medicine. Microscopically, cells with ruptured membranes and stratified cytoplasm (necrosis, apoptosis) were identified, and giant tumour cells appeared with large nuclei (Fig. 9).

The results of this study, taking into account the assessment of cell survival and morphological characteristics in micropreparations, testify to the antitumor effect of the combined use of laser irradiation and doxorubicin. It should be noted that an infrared laser caused the most pronounced cytotoxic effect on the resistant cells of MCF7-DOX culture with a wavelength of 810 nm. Our experiment demonstrated that the infrared laser light, combined with the toxic effect of doxorubicin, creates the conditions for tumour cell apoptosis.

4. Discussion

Laser medicine has been developing intensively, especially in the last 20 years. In modern works, the effects of light energy with different wavelengths, exposure and power of lasers are studied. As with all lasers, the biological effects of infrared light exposure depend on the photoacceptor molecule. A leading hypothesis explaining how light increases the activity of the enzyme cytochrome c oxidase (CCO) is that nitric oxide (a molecule known to inhibit CCO by noncovalent binding between heme-a₃ and CuB) can be photodissociated by absorbing photons of infrared light. One theory explaining why photobiomodulation has a more significant effect on diseased or damaged cells and tissues and does not dramatically affect healthy cells is that unhealthy or hypoxic cells are more likely to have an inhibitory concentration of NO [18, 19].

Goerge et al. [20] in studies of low-energy lasers (LEL) recorded an increase in the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) in primary fibroblasts of the skin; the infrared laser is also proposed as a likely helpful tool for future synergistic cancer phototherapy [21].

Research has also established that LEL reduced the proliferation of oral cavity carcinoma cells: increased the proportion of S-phase cells, decreased the proportion of G1-phase cells and provoked a pro-apoptotic effect [22].

Alexandratou et al. found transient increases in mitochondrial membrane potential and intracellular calcium along with increased ROS production and stimulation of cytoplasmic alkalisation, demonstrating multiple aspects of LEL-induced mitochondrial changes [23].

A study by Chen et al. showed that LEL (810 nm) induces ROS and ATP production with NF-κB activation in mouse embryonic fibroblasts [24].

The theory of the mechanism of action of photobiomodulation on cells states that photon radiation directly or indirectly targets DNA and the genome pool. Free radicals (including ROS) are formed under indirect, low laser radiation. High levels of ROS are known to be cytotoxic, leading to the disruption of numerous signalling cascades. Even at low levels, ROS can induce apoptosis in MCF-4 breast cancer and MC3T3 preosteoblastic cells by acting as secondary mediators of various signalling pathways [25, 26].

The study of Golovynska et al. 2021 reported on the effects of low-intensity light at 650, 808, and 1064 nm on neurons and two types of cancer cells (neuroblastoma and HeLa), focusing on photoinduced changes in intracellular Ca²⁺ ion levels and related signalling pathways. The obtained results show that 650 and 808 nm light promotes intracellular Ca²⁺ increase regardless of the cell type, but with different dynamics due to the peculiarities of Ca²⁺ regulation in neurons and cancer cells. Two causes responsible for the increase in Ca²⁺ have been identified: the influx of exogenous Ca²⁺ ions into cells and the release of Ca²⁺ from the endoplasmic reticulum. The release of Ca²⁺ from the endoplasmic reticulum, activated by the formation of reactive oxygen species, is considered a possible light-dependent signalling pathway [27].

It has also been established that the effects of laser light are primarily manifested in the functioning of the structures most vulnerable to irradiation in the cell - mitochondrial membranes [28, 29]. The mitochondrial membrane is the most important and, accordingly, the most sensitive part of this organelle to various influences [30]. The impact on mitochondria causes an increase in the production of reactive oxygen species, which in a normal damaged cell can serve as a prerequisite for activity augmentation and an improvement in the ability to recover [31, 32].

On the contrary, in an atypical cell, in which the synthesis of ROS can be initially more intense because of the influence of laser, there is a risk of forming a pathological circle – due to the stimulation of ROS-induced additional production of ROS [33, 34].

Compared to normal cells, in which mitochondrial redox processes, in particular the regulation of the synthesis of reactive oxygen species, are in dynamic equilibrium, in damaged cells (in case of inflammation and/or hypoxia) there is a violation of the regulation of oxygen metabolism and decrease in the reparative potential. In this case, laser irradiation can simulate redox cascades and promote cell regeneration. Conversely, excessive ROS synthesis occurs in atypical cells due to increased metabolic activity [35]. When a laser is exposed to such a cell against the background of increased synthesis of ROS, modulation of this process occurs, which leads to the so-called ROS-induced ROS release, which increases the activity of pro-apoptotic regulators [36, 37] (**Fig. 10**).

Fig. 10. Mechanisms of pro-apoptotic action of laser irradiation

In a normal cell (A), redox processes, as well as regulation of ROS synthesis, are in dynamic equilibrium; in the damaged cell (B), there is a violation of the regulation of oxygen metabolism, a decrease in the reparative potential against the background of hypoxia, and in this case, the laser can simulate redox cascades and promote cell recovery; in atypical cells (C) due to increased metabolic activity, excessive synthesis of ROS occurs; during laser exposure to a malignant cell (D) against the background of increased synthesis of ROS, this process is modulated, which leads to the so-called ROS-induced ROS release, the activity of pro-apoptotic regulators increases; the cell goes into apoptosis [36, 37].

Joining the light energy to the cytotoxic effect of doxorubicin not only provokes an increase in the activity of pro-apoptotic regulators. After all, against the background of oxidative stress, cell apoptosis is accompanied by disruption of mitochondrial DNA functions, destruction of membrane microstructures, and inhibition of metabolic processes [38]. Such changes lead to violations of vital processes, first directly at the level of mitochondria – and then, predictably, conditions are created for critical damage already at the cellular level [39, 40]. The dynamic balance of metabolic processes that underlie the restoration or, conversely, the degradation of the cell's vital functions is disturbed [41, 42]. Apoptosis due to ROS-induced ROS production can be a predictable phenomenon because it is an evolutionarily programmed scenario if metabolic changes become incompatible

with normal functioning [43, 44]. The initiation of apoptosis processes may seem all the more likely when we understand that destructive changes in the cell are generated not by one but by several influencing factors: laser irradiation and doxorubicin [45, 46].

According to our own opinion and according to the data of the scientific literature, doxorubicin, as a cytotoxic factor, when exposed to an intact cell, provokes ROS-induced ROS release and activates caspase-3 [47, 48]. Excess synthesis of ROS also occurs when doxorubicin affects a malignant cell. As a result of DNA damage, the complex-1-dependent cascade of ROS formation with the participation of p53 is stimulated, and the caspase system and BAX activity increases – the cell enters apoptosis [49] (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11. Mechanisms of pro-apoptotic action of doxorubicin

In a normal cell (A), redox processes, in particular regulation of ROS synthesis, are in dynamic equilibrium; when doxorubicin affects an intact cell (B), ROS-induced excessive release of ROS is observed, caspase-3 is activated; in atypical cells (C) due to increased metabolic activity, excessive synthesis of ROS occurs. When doxorubicin affects a malignant cell (D) due to DNA damage, the complex-1-dependent cascade of ROS formation with the participation of p53 is stimulated, the activity of the caspase system and BAX increases; the cell goes into apoptosis [48, 49].

In the context of the above data, the combination of infrared laser radiation with the use of doxorubicin seemed all the more logical to us. After all, the most studied mechanism of action of doxorubicin today is the medicine's ability to integrate into pairs of DNA bases, causing DNA strand breaks and inhibiting the synthesis of both DNA and RNA [50]. Doxorubicin inhibits the enzyme topoisomerase II, causing DNA damage and induction of apoptosis [51, 52]. Such effects of doxorubicin are joined by the pro-apoptotic effect of laser irradiation through ROS-induced ROS release, as well as through the activation of apoptosis regulators, which we present in the integrated scheme (Fig. 12).

Doxorubicin integrates into DNA, disrupts its synthesis, and stimulates apoptosis by inhibiting topoisomerase II. In addition, infrared light activates cytochrome C oxidase, provokes the release of calcium ions from the endoplasmic reticulum, and causes ROS-induced ROS to release and then activate pro-apoptotic regulators.

The presented concept summarises data from various sources of literature [35–55] and the results of my own research. It provides a basis for understanding those photobiological

and metabolic processes that occur in the cell during the combined effect of doxorubicin and laser light.

Fig. 12. Integrated scheme of the mechanisms of the combined effect of infrared laser and doxorubicin on intracellular processes that lead to apoptosis

Our assessment of tumor cell growth and morphological changes, which we performed using light microscopy, confirms that different periods of cultivation with doxorubicin and using different laser wavelengths lead to different results.

Application of laser irradiation with a wavelength of both 660 nm and 810 nm is predicted to lead to inhibition of cell proliferation of MCF-7 culture sensitive to the chemotherapeutic agent in all groups of culture with doxorubicin: after 15, 30, 60 and 90 minutes.

On the other hand, the doxorubicin-resistant MCF-7DOX culture showed sensitivity to cytotoxic effects only when exposed to a laser with a wavelength of 810 nm and only in groups with 60- and 90-min exposure to doxorubicin before the start of irradiation.

Limitations of the study. Light microscopy of cell cultures made it possible to assess growth features and some signs of apoptosis. However, for a more detailed study of the influence of cytotoxic factors at the micro level, electron microscopy data may be needed, as well as for assessing apoptosis – analysis of the expression of pro-apoptotic regulators.

Prospects for further research. Understanding the mechanisms of the effect of laser and doxorubicin on metabolic processes in the cell, in particular, the stimulation of ROS-induced ROS release opens up prospects for expanding the spectrum of research in this direction, using different cell models, chemotherapeutic medicines and different parameters of laser radiation.

5. Conclusions

The study's results allow us to consider infrared laser light as a factor affecting tumour cells, which can act synergistically with doxorubicin. It is significant that it was after combining doxorubicin with infrared laser irradiation with a wavelength of 810 nm that the doxorubicin-resistant MCF-7DOX cell culture experienced a marked cytotoxic effect.

It is the infrared laser, in combination with doxorubicin, probably due to its effect on mitochondria and modulation of the process of ROS-induced ROS release, that creates the conditions for tumor cells to undergo apoptosis, which is confirmed by cytomorphological data of light microscopy.

The action of infrared laser light in synergy with doxorubicin and the creation of conditions for tumor cells to undergo apoptosis is the opening of prospects for studying the possibilities of reducing the treatment toxicity of malignant neoplasms due to a possible reduction in the dose of the chemotherapeutic agent.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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